
Date: 11 May 2018
To: DART Project
From: Siegfried Ettl & Steve Chesley, 392R
Subject: Post-Deflection Impact Risk Assessment of DART Mission

Summary

This memorandum contains describes the results of a post-deflection impact risk assessment (PDIRA) of the Double Asteroid Redirection Test (DART, e.g., Cheng et al. 2016). DART is a mission concept intended to demonstrate the change of the state of motion of an asteroid through a kinetic impact. By targeting the satellite of the near-Earth asteroid 65803 Didymos in October 2022, DART would alter the orbital period of the binary asteroid system. Measurements of the change in the mutual orbital period of the binary system would inform kinetic impactor based deflection techniques.

The DART impact would also result in a change of Didymos' orbit around the sun. Didymos is a near Earth object and classified as potentially hazardous asteroid (PHA). This document addresses concerns about planetary safety that may arise as a result of DART altering the heliocentric orbit of Didymos. To this end, we performed a PDIRA based on a statistical evaluation of the effect that DART is likely to have on Didymos' heliocentric orbit.

Our results indicate that DART would not significantly alter the probability of the Didymos system to collide with the Earth within the next 150 years. The closest encounter between Didymos and our planet in the next one and a half centuries will occur in 2123 where Didymos has less than a one in a trillion chance to come within 15 lunar distances (roughly 5.9 million kilometers or 3.6 million miles) of the Earth.

The DART mission concept

The current DART mission design features a single spacecraft launched on 15 June 2021. According to trajectory proposition D18A31-TL28F-21F15-V001 (APL/JPL) DART would fly by another near-Earth asteroid, 138971 (2001 CB21), before colliding with the moonlet of asteroid 65803 Didymos on 5th October 2022 at 15:03:06 UTC with a relative speed of approximately 6 km/s. Together with the predicted arrival mass of 585.722 kg, the DART impact would result in a $\sim 7 \mu\text{m/s}$ change of the heliocentric velocity of the Didymos system (ΔV) assuming no momentum transport through crater ejecta ($\beta=1$). However, uncertainties related to the deflection, such as the amount of momentum added by crater ejecta, make it difficult to predict the final ΔV imparted on the Didymos system. This leads to an increased uncertainty in the asteroid's post-deflection orbit.

Post-Deflection Impact Risk Analysis (PDIRA)

The purpose of a post-mitigation or post-deflection impact risk assessment (PMIRA, PDIRA Ettl et al. 2015) is to dispel concerns that an asteroid deflection maneuver would significantly increase the risk of a future collision between the target asteroid and the Earth. By analyzing how the envisioned changes in the target's heliocentric orbit affect the asteroid's Earth impact probabilities, planetary safety concerns can be addressed in a quantitative fashion. Uncertainties in the target asteroid's orbit as well as in the deflection process necessitate a statistical approach.

The PDIRA for DART included the following steps:

1. Possible impact locations on the moonlet of Didymos (henceforth "Didymoon") were evaluated in accordance with the current DART trajectory (D18A31-TL28F-21F15-V001) as well as guidance, navigation and control (GNC) targeting uncertainties.

2. In addition to the momentum imparted by the spacecraft itself, crater ejecta can influence the magnitude and direction of Didymos’ heliocentric velocity. By sampling probable net ejecta momentum vectors, statistical distributions of the change in the heliocentric velocity of the center of mass of the Didymos system were generated. The model presented in Scheeres et al. (2015) was used to correlate ejecta momentum directions with the impact location on Didymoon.
3. The resulting uncertainty in ΔV was combined with the orbit uncertainty at the time of impact. The combined uncertainties were propagated to future close approaches between the Didymos system and the Earth. The closest approaches occurred in the years 2062 and 2123.
4. At each close approach the position of the nominal orbit solution (JPL 134) as well as the orbit solutions resulting from a DART impact were mapped onto the Earth-asteroid encounter plane (B-plane), see Figure 1. This made it possible to assess how DART would alter the orbit of the Didymos system and whether or not the change in Didymos’ orbit could significantly heighten its risk to impact the Earth.

Table 1: Parameter ranges and uncertainties assumed in the PDIRA study of DART.

Parameter	Nominal Value	Uncertainty/Range
Didymos reference orbit	JPL 134 (Appendix A)	JPL 134 orbit uncertainty
Impact time	JD 2459858.12795666 (TDB) JD 2459858.12715592 (UTC)	± 1 JD
Mass of Didymos system	5.278×10^{11} kg	$\pm 1.62 \times 10^{11}$ kg (3σ uniform)
Mass of DART impactor	585.722 kg	no uncertainty
DART reference trajectory	D18A31-TL28F-21F15-V001	no uncertainty
DART GNC / targeting	likely envelope full envelope	± 45 m (3σ Gaussian) hemisphere accessible to DART
BETA (β)	likely envelope full envelope	[1.01, 3.01] (uniform) [1.01, 10.01] (uniform)
Surface normal orientation <i>(angle between DART impact vector and surface normal)</i>	likely envelope (Appendix B) full envelope (Appendix B)	[97.8, 180] deg / projection of GNC targeting plane onto Didymoon reference ellipsoid (Gaussian targeting) [90, 180] deg / projection of GNC targeting planet onot entire hemisphere accessible to DART (uniform targeting)

Four scenarios were considered. The ‘likely envelope’ scenario (A) features expected variations in the targeting and ejecta momentum vectors. The ‘full envelope’ scenario (B) covers all possible ejecta momentum directions and a wide range of momentum enhancement factors. The corresponding values are provided in Table 1.

The other two scenarios (C & D) feature ‘full envelope’ uncertainties with the DART impact date being varied. In scenario C, the impact occurs 24 hours earlier, on October 4th 2022. Scenario D assumes the impact is delayed by one day (October 6th 2022). The latter two scenarios are meant to account for potential maneuvers of the DART spacecraft that may be necessary to achieve the desired impact geometry.

Figure 1: An illustration of the B-plane. The red line corresponds to the nominal orbit of an asteroid during a close approach with the Earth. The unit vector \hat{S} points along the incoming asymptote of the unperturbed asteroid trajectory relative to the Earth. The other coordinates in the Öpik frame are $\hat{\xi} = \hat{v}_p \times \hat{S}$, where v_p is the Earth’s heliocentric velocity, and $\hat{\zeta} = -\hat{S} \times \hat{\xi}$.

Post-Deflection Impact Risk Assessment Results

The two closest approaches of the Didymos system to the Earth after the DART impact occur in the years 2062 and 2123. The results of the PDIRA study for these encounters are presented in Figures 2 and 3, respectively. The distance to the Earth of the nominal solutions are approximately 19.4 lunar distances (LD), roughly 7.4×10^6 km, in 2062 and 15.3 LD in 2123 (roughly 5.9×10^6 km). The first plot of each Figure shows both the Earth and the asteroid in the B-plane to provide a to-scale view of the respective encounter. The second plot (bottom left) shows a to-scale detail of the encounter prediction uncertainty ellipsoids projected onto the B-plane ($3\text{-}\sigma$), and the third plot presents a not-to-scale depiction of the B-plane footprints. Note that the bottom panels are centered on the nominal (no deflection) position of Didymos on the B-plane. The direction and distance to the Earth is marked by arrows. The bottom panels feature scenarios A and B, i.e. DART impacts with ‘likely’ (blue) and ‘full envelope’ (green) uncertainties next to the nominal, not deflected orbit solution (black). All three solutions have been generated using JPL’s standard numerical propagation and covariance mapping techniques. In order to validate those results we performed Monte Carlo simulations for scenario B (red) that were in good agreement with the covariance mappings.

A DART impact would indeed modify encounter distances with the Earth, as can be seen in Figures 2 and 3. Such changes are only on the order of several tens of kilometers, however, and well within current orbit uncertainties. Given the relatively small ΔV values that DART would deliver to the Didymos system, orbit uncertainties rather than deflection related uncertainties dominate the uncertainties in the encounter distance.

Figure 2: Encounter (B-plane) maps of the Didymos system with and without a DART impact. The top panel shows the encounter with the Earth in 2062 to scale. The lower panels present the nominal, non-deflected solution (JPL 134) as well as the 3σ uncertainty ellipse in black. DART impact scenarios A and B are colored blue and green, respectively. Monte Carlo simulation based validation points are shown in red.

Figure 3: Same as Figure 2, but for the close approach in the year 2123 between Didymos and the Earth.

A comparison between the extent of the uncertainty domains and the Earth encounter distances shows that the probability of finding the Didymos system at Earth distances of less than 19.4 LD in 2062 and 15.3 LD in 2123 is practically negligible.

Scenarios C and D, which have the DART impact shifted by ± 1 day, lead to Earth encounters within several kilometers of scenario B and with comparable uncertainty regions. They are, therefore, not explicitly shown in the plots.

Scenario B covers a wider range in possible deflection ΔV values than scenario A, hence the larger size of the corresponding uncertainty region. Scenario B also shows a greater mean deflection compared to scenario A which is due to the fact that the former has a higher expected momentum enhancement value (Table 1).

Conclusions

We conducted a post-deflection impact risk assessment for the current DART mission concept. Our results indicate that

- the DART impact in 2022 would slightly modify the heliocentric orbit of 65803 Didymos,
- the change in the Didymos orbit resulting from the DART impact is small and falls within current orbit uncertainties,
- the Didymos system is extremely unlikely (less than one in a trillion chance) to approach the Earth closer than 19.4 LD within the next hundred years and 15.3 LD within the next one hundred fifty years, and
- a shift of ± 1 day in the impact date for DART would not change the above results noticeably, assuming the impact velocity and geometry do not change substantially.

We conclude that the DART mission as currently envisioned would not raise planetary safety concerns.

References

Cheng, A. F., Michel, P., Jutzi, M., Rivkin, A. S., Stickle, A., Barnouin, O., ... & Richardson, D. C. (2016). Asteroid impact & deflection assessment mission: kinetic impactor. *Planetary and space science*, 121, 27-35.

Eggl, S., Hestroffer, D., Thuillot, W., Bancelin, D., Cano, J. L., & Cichocki, F. (2015). Post mitigation impact risk analysis for asteroid deflection demonstration missions. *Advances in Space Research*, 56(3), 528-548.

Scheeres, D. J., McMahon, J. W., Jones, B. A., & Doostan, A. (2015, March). Variation of delivered impulse as a function of asteroid shape. In *Aerospace Conference, 2015 IEEE* (pp. 1-7). IEEE.

Appendix A

JPL orbit solution 134 for 65803 Didymos. Retrieved from <https://ssd.jpl.nasa.gov/sbdb.cgi>, 04/31/2018.

Orbital Elements at Epoch 2457800.5 (2017-Feb-16.0) TDB
Reference: **JPL 134** (heliocentric ecliptic J2000)

Element	Value	Uncertainty (1-sigma)	Units	
e	.3838328705983211	9.8107e-09		
a	1.644588561816618	7.7121e-09	au	
q	1.013341413181381	1.8414e-08	au	
i	3.407679182063813	3.275e-06	deg	
node	73.22185799635652	2.3681e-05	deg	
peri	319.2515891346795	2.6016e-05	deg	
M	110.7962199046193	1.7727e-05	deg	
tp	2457563.413531463186 (2016-Jun-23.91353146)	3.6274e-05	JED	
period	770.3433271164755	5.4187e-06	d	
		2.11	1.484e-08	yr
n	.4673240973573958	3.2872e-09	deg/d	
Q	2.275835710451855	1.0672e-08	au	

Orbit Determination Parameters

# obs. used (total)	863
# delay obs. used	6
# Doppler obs. used	0
data-arc span	7686 days (21.04 yr)
first obs. used	1996-04-11
last obs. used	2017-04-27
planetary ephem.	DE431
SB-perf. ephem.	SB431-N16
condition code	0
fit RMS	.32267
data source	ORB
producer	Davide Farnocchia
solution date	2018-Apr-04 12:07:24

Additional Information

Earth MOID =	.0406808 au
Jupiter MOID =	3.16266 au
T_jup =	4.200

[hide covariance matrix]

Orbital Elements at Epoch 2455355.5 (2010-Jun-08.0) TDB
Reference: **JPL 134** (heliocentric ecliptic J2000)

Element	Value	Uncertainty (1-sigma)	Units
e	.3837607188448682	9.8103e-09	
q	1.013336919856051	1.8434e-08	au
tp	2455252.755582395395 (2010-Feb-25.25558240)	2.002e-05	JED
node	73.2465558179597	2.3675e-05	deg
peri	319.1969779642492	2.6013e-05	deg
i	3.407766683561805	3.2746e-06	deg

Orbit Determination Parameters

# obs. used (total)	863
# delay obs. used	6
# Doppler obs. used	0
data-arc span	7686 days (21.04 yr)
first obs. used	1996-04-11
last obs. used	2017-04-27
planetary ephem.	DE431
SB-perf. ephem.	SB431-N16
condition code	0
fit RMS	.32267
data source	ORB
producer	Davide Farnocchia
solution date	2018-Apr-04 12:07:24

Additional Information

Jupiter MOID =	3.16266 au
T_jup =	4.200

Orbit Covariance (6x6)

	e	q	tp	node	peri	i
e	9.62423448957937E-17	-1.754739146905293E-16	-1.066817621951305E-13	1.000369213820474E-13	-1.592243284638727E-13	5.027955832471125E-15
q	-1.754739146905293E-16	3.398234856572292E-16	2.693749962430511E-13	-1.801272813798773E-13	2.963585082678332E-13	-9.985407389674163E-15
tp	-1.066817621951305E-13	2.693749962430511E-13	4.008161204717423E-10	-8.477496354677991E-11	1.825815015025491E-10	-1.078944754901697E-11
node	1.000369213820474E-13	-1.801272813798773E-13	-8.477496354677991E-11	5.605161122614435E-10	-5.976533172500188E-10	-4.582105586180596E-11
peri	-1.592243284638727E-13	2.963585082678332E-13	1.825815015025491E-10	-5.976533172500188E-10	6.766982567192859E-10	4.167941033141654E-11
i	5.027955832471125E-15	-9.985407389674163E-15	-1.078944754901697E-11	-4.582105586180596E-11	4.167941033141654E-11	1.072326102313266E-11

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Appendix B

The following models were used to generate likely ejecta momentum vectors. The ejecta vector distribution in the “likely envelope” scenario (A) was calculated from a projection of the GNC targeting plane (orthogonal to the impact vector) onto the Didymoon reference ellipsoid. The uncertainty in the targeting was assumed to follow a bivariate Gaussian distribution in the targeting plane with a standard deviation of 15m. The semiaxes of the Didymoon reference ellipsoid were $a=103.677\text{m}$, $b=79.752\text{m}$, $c=66.460\text{m}$. Net ejecta momenta were assumed to follow the direction of the respective surface normal (e.g. Scheeres et al. 2015). The distribution of surface normals was, in turn, determined by the impact configuration. The resulting distribution of the angle between the DART impact vector and the surface normal is shown in Figure 5. Given the unknown surface properties of Didymoon, scenario B featured a uniform sampling of the targeting area projected onto the entire accessible hemisphere, whereby a spherical model for Didymoon was chosen. The corresponding distribution of impact angles is also given in Figure 5.

Figure 4: Visualization of the ejecta vector sampling in the likely envelope scenario (A). The x-axis of the body-fixed frame points towards Didymos. The angle between the DART impact vector and the surface normal is color coded. Hot colors indicate anti-alignment of the impact vector and the surface normal. Cool colors mark configurations close to orthogonality.

Figure 5: The distribution of angles between the impact vector of the DART spacecraft and Didymoon's surface normals for the likely and full envelope scenarios (A and B), respectively.